

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

A NEW METHOD OF FUEL COMBUSTION. KUZNETSOV'S FMG SYSTEM.

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Abstract

The article discusses a new fuel combustion method developed in Russia and patented as the "Kuznetsov free gas motion (FGM) system". It provides a comparison with the traditional "forced gas motion (FGM) system" that has been used worldwide for many centuries. It is noted that the FGM system has significant drawbacks in terms of ecology and fuel combustion efficiency.

The Kuznetsov FGM system implements a fundamentally new approach to organizing the combustion process, based on the separation of gases by degree of heating and the multiple use of combustion products (CO₂ and H₂O) as additional fuel. This increases energy efficiency and minimizes harmful emissions into the atmosphere.

The article emphasizes the need for the global energy sector to transition to the Kuznetsov FGM system as a more environmentally friendly and rational alternative to the traditional FGM fuel combustion method.

Keywords: Free gas motion (FGM) system, Forced gas motion (FGM) system, Fuel combustion method, Energy efficiency, Environmental friendliness, Basic material.

The "forced gas motion" (FGM) system, the method of burning fuel has been studied and used by mankind for many millennia. Its disadvantages are dirty and inefficient combustion, creating an environmental problem, the greenhouse effect.

Therefore, the new "free gas motion (FGM) Kuznetsov system" is difficult for scientists, manufacturers of heat generators and stove makers who make stoves of the old system to comprehend. We interfere with them, it is difficult to reconfigure the equipment, production. In the USA and the European Union there are no experts in the "FGM system" who can give a positive conclusion on it. This hinders its integration into world energy, as well as the mentioned countries.

In 1777, the French scientist A. Lavoisier created an oxygen theory of combustion. He described the oxidation-reduction combustion reaction. These are counter-current parallel chemical reactions occurring simultaneously. However, no one has been able to create conditions for its flow.

In Russia, I have patented 2 invention patents: No. 2055272 of 02/27/1996 and No. 2553748 of 05/22/2015, which created the conditions for its flow. The first patent, "the furnace and the hood are united into a single space." Practically, a "dry seam" was made between the furnace and the hood (a gap 2-3 cm wide), providing heat exchange between them. Heat exchange occurs similarly if you open the door to the street in winter. This made it possible to divide the gases in the furnace according to the degree of heating. In the combustion process, the amount of air required for combustion must be supplied to the furnace in each time period. In the FGM system, if you supply less, there will be incomplete combustion and particle emissions into the flue, polluting the air. If more air is supplied, the hot CO₂ and H₂O gases, the product of the combustion reaction, are diluted with cold air and the efficiency of the stove is reduced. For this reason, when testing FGM stoves, the results of the first and last 5 minutes are not taken into account. But this is self-deception.

In the FGM system, plenty of air is supplied at any time period. The amount of oxygen required for the combustion reaction is involved. There is a separation of gases according to the degree of heating. Ballast gases with an increased nitrogen content leave the flue. Warm air comes out of the flue with a properly constructed stove/boiler/heat generator. This has been confirmed in many countries around the world where we have held seminars.

The hot gases, the product of the combustion reaction, enter the upper part of the hood and will not come out of the hood until they give up their heat. In the grate area, fuel gasification. Hydrocarbons rise through the center of the furnace. When exposed to oxygen, CO₂ and H₂O are obtained, the product of the combustion reaction. In this case, stoves/boilers are obtained with an efficiency approximately 30% higher than FGM stoves/boilers. They do not meet the requirements for combustion purity. Drawings of such stoves are posted on my website, <http://stove.ru/products>. These drawings are used in many countries around the world, including North America, http://www.stovemaster.com/html_en/designsyshistory.html

In the FGM system, according to the second patent, we supply secondary air to the oxidation zone. In this case, the spent hot CO₂ and H₂O gases descend along the walls, towards the hydrocarbon.

A new method of burning fuel, the FGM Kuznetsov system.

I did this. The essence of combustion in the FGM system is that the blown combustion reactions CO₂ and H₂O do not go into the flue, but are reduced to fuel, 2CO and water gas, which are again oxidized (burned) to CO₂ and H₂O. This continues as long as fuel burns in the furnace. The fuel is wood with a high content of volatiles.

Stoves of the new FGM system (free gas motion), built in accordance with my

Russian Federation invention patents: No. 2055272 of 02/27/1996 and No. 2553748 of 05/22/2015, METHOD OF BURNING FUEL.

Please note the abbreviations FGM is forced gas motion, and FGM is free gas motion

Fig.3

Here is the English translation with FGM for forced gas motion and FGM for free gas motion:

In their combustion chamber combined with the convective system, the flow of the gas stream generated during the fuel combustion occurs due to the heat exchange processes with equal air supply and draft.

The new method of burning fuel, the "FGM System", differs fundamentally from the "FGM system". For many centuries they have studied and applied it. Therefore, the new system is difficult for scientists, manufacturers of heat generators and stove makers who make stoves of the old system to comprehend. We interfere with them, it is difficult to reconfigure the equipment, production. In the USA and the European Union there are no experts in the "FGM system" who can give a positive conclusion about it. This hinders its integration into world energy, as well as the mentioned countries. In many countries there are our students, including the USA, and people making stoves according to our free FGM system drawings on my website. They also cannot be considered experts.

We are happy to share with you information about the new fuel combustion system known as the "Kuznetsov FGM", which was developed and patented in Russia. This innovative technology solves the problems of ecology and combustion efficiency that accompany the traditional "FGM System".

Currently, many countries spend huge resources on the FGM system, but it does not solve issues related to environmental friendliness and fuel combustion efficiency. Problems such as air pollution and the greenhouse effect remain relevant, despite significant financial costs.

The "Kuznetsov FGM" system offers a revolutionary solution that allows overcoming these problems. It is based on the conversion of CO₂ and H₂O gases formed during combustion into fuel, which is then burned again. Thus, we not only eliminate the emission of harmful gases into the atmosphere, but also obtain additional fuel for use.

The introduction of the FGM system opens up new prospects for improving fuel combustion efficiency and reducing negative environmental impacts. This innovative solution will significantly reduce the environmental problems we face today, while using available resources more efficiently.

We urge you to consider the Kuznetsov FGM system as an alternative to the FGM system. It not only solves the problems of ecology and combustion efficiency, but is also a more cost-effective solution in the long term. The transition to the new system will help optimize costs, reduce environmental pollution, and create a more sustainable and environmentally responsible future energy system.

Nature of the earth is created by the Supreme Mind, everything in it is balanced, self-regulating and optimal. A human is himself a particle of nature and created by it. Therefore, a person is not given to create something more perfect. He must identify the laws of nature, study and follow them. In all our activities, we try to follow this principle.

The system of free gas motion - the Kuznetsov FGM System. (It should be noted that this name is reflected in the documents of the MINISTRY OF ENERGY of the RUSSIAN FEDERATION). It provides unlimited opportunities to build environmentally friendly and efficient heat generators for various functional purposes and capacities.

The essence of the combustion process is that already in the FGM Kuznetsov system furnace, there is a separation of gases by degree of heating, into heat carriers (CO₂, H₂O) and ballast gases (my RF patent 2055272). The heat of the hot gases is not lost. The hot gases are directed to the hood, where they give up heat, descend down along the walls of the hood and exit through the flue. Energy efficiency of stoves increases, however carbon dioxide CO₂ is released into the atmosphere. In stoves with rotations, FGM system, hot gases together with ballast gases immediately exit through the flue.

Translate to English and also note the abbreviations FGM is Free Gas Motion and FGM is Forced Gas Motion.

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